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Research Article

Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers Vis-À-Vis Teachers Efficiency in Work Performance

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ABSTRACT

Toropova (2021) stated that teacher job satisfaction merits closer attention. Not only is job satisfaction closely related to teacher retention, but it also contributes to the well-being of teachers and their over-all efficiency in work performance. The study generally aimed at determining the teachers' job satisfaction and teacher's efficiency in work performance. This quantitative study made use of a descriptive survey design to find out the teacher job satisfaction towards teachers efficiency in work performance of secondary school teacher in the Districts of Naval, Division of Biliran. Furthermore, the respondents of this study composed of 142 teachers in the secondary schools of Districts I-IV of Naval in the Division of Biliran. Stratified random sampling was employed in choosing the teacher respondents of this study so that there will be appropriate representation of the teachers per school. It has been revealed that the teachers' job satisfaction reached an over-all result of being satisfied in the workplace. This implies that the teachers felt contented if they are comfortable in their work. This can still be enhanced by actively working and collaborating with school heads and stakeholders for the betterment and improvement of the teachers in the workplace. On the other hand, teachers believed their efficiency to be quite a bit which entails the need for them to be motivated and empowered in their job. This can be done through peer mentoring or counselling. Proper and adequate technical assistance should also be provided to teachers, most especially those with low performance at school.

Keywords: Public Secondary School Teachers, teacher's job satisfaction, teacher's efficiency

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INTRODUCTION

Toropova (2021) specified that teacher shortage is an international problem thus, teacher job satisfaction merits closer attention. Not only is job satisfaction closely related to teacher retention, but it also contributes to the well-being of teachers and their over-all work performance or work efficiency.

Being said, teacher job satisfaction has many important and far-reaching implications. First, it contributes to teacher well-being as satisfied teachers are less susceptible to stress and burnout (Kyriacou, et.al, 1977; Skaalvik, 2011). In addition, there is evidence that teachers who are content with their job also feel better (Collie, et.al, 2012, Spilt, et.al, 2011). Furthermore, as Kunter, et.al (2013) stated that satisfied teachers offer higher instructional quality and better learning support for their students. This simply means that content teachers demonstrate stronger job commitment and are less prone to leave the profession (Blömeke, 2017).

On the other hand, Klassen et al. (2009) states that teachers' self-efficacy has progressively gained an important role in school psychology research as a result of its implications for teaching effectiveness, instructional practices, and for students' academic achievement. Considerable research has shown that teachers with high levels of self-efficacy experience higher levels of job satisfaction, lower levels of job-related stress and face less difficulties in dealing with students' misbehaviors (Caprara et.al, 2003). Moreover, Djigić (2014) found out that teachers with higher levels of openness to experience and conscientiousness reported a stronger sense of efficacy. Therefore, improved teacher self-efficacy can result in improved teacher mental health and job satisfaction, and students' academic performance (Bandura, 1977).

Toward this end, the researcher opted to conduct the study to clearly determine the teachers' job satisfaction vis-à-vis teachers' efficiency in work

performance in the Districts of Naval I-IV, Naval, Biliran Province.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study generally aimed at determining the teachers' job satisfaction and teacher's efficiency in work performance. Specifically, purportedly aimed to: 1) Ascertain the teachers' job satisfaction; 2) Determine the teachers' efficiency in work performance; 3) Design a Training and Development Program for Teachers.

METHODOLOGY

This quantitative study made use of a descriptive survey design to find out the teacher's job satisfaction and efficiency in work performance of secondary school teacher in the Districts of Naval, Division of Biliran. Moreover, this study took place in the Districts of Naval I-IV, Naval, Biliran Province. It was participated only by the public secondary schools; where no such study had been made in the past and the researcher being a secondary school teacher.

Furthermore, the respondents of this study composed of 142 teachers in the secondary schools of Districts I-IV of Naval in the Division of Biliran. Stratified random sampling was employed in choosing the teacher respondents of this study so that there will be appropriate representation of the teachers per school. For teacher respondents, the survey questionnaire was composed of two parts: Part I was the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire, Copyright 1977. It was lifted from the Vocational Psychology Research, University of Minnesota, USA which is composed of 20 items and a five point Likert Scale: 5- Very Satisfied; 4- Satisfied; 3- Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied, 2Dissatisfied and 1-Very Dissatisfied. Part II was the Teacher Sense of Efficacy Scale (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk-Hoy, 2001) designed to help us gain a better understanding of the kinds of things that create difficulties for teachers in their school activities. It utilized a five point Likert scale: 5-

A Great Deal, 4- Quite A Bit, 3- Some Influence, 2- Very Little, and 1- Nothing.

Teachers' Job Satisfaction

The table below presents the level of teachers' job satisfaction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter discusses the analysis of the data gathered with their corresponding presentation: Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Teachers' Efficiency

Table 1. Teachers' Job Satisfaction

No.	Statement	WM	Description
1.	Being able to keep busy all the time	3.68	Satisfied
2	The chance to work alone on the job	3.56	Satisfied
3	The chance to do different things from time to time	3.67	Satisfied
4	The chance to be "somebody" in the community	3.51	Satisfied
5	The way my boss handles his/her workers	3.54	Satisfied
6	The competence of my supervisor in making decisions	3.59	Satisfied
7	Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience	3.50	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
8	The way my job provides for steady employment	3.89	Satisfied
9	The chance to do things for other people	3.77	Satisfied
10	The chance to tell people what to do	3.56	Satisfied
11	The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	3.65	Satisfied
12	The way company policies are put into practice	3.50	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
13	My pay and the amount of work I do	3.56	Satisfied
14	The chances for advancement on this job	3.52	Satisfied
15	The freedom to use my own judgment	3.58	Satisfied
16	The chance to try my own methods of doing the job	3.63	Satisfied
17	The working conditions	3.49	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
18	The way my co-workers get along with each other	3.70	Satisfied
19	The praise I get for doing a good job	3.65	Satisfied
20	The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	3.63	Satisfied
	AWM	3.61	Satisfied

The table above shows the responses of the teachers as to their level of job satisfaction which revealed an over-all result as “Satisfied” (AWM=3.61). It is evidently shown in the aforcited table that teachers' job satisfaction is imperative as to extreme weighted mean of 3.89 with a satisfied description in the indicator, “the way my job provides for steady employment.” In this manner, having a regular salary means a lot to them. However, in the indicator “the working conditions” showed the lowest weighted mean of 3.49 neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. The result means that in terms of job satisfaction most of them were just satisfied on their job.

This implies that the teachers felt contented and/or satisfied if they are comfortable in their work. Based on the evidence acquisition, in the study of Velmurugan (2016) in his statements that in order to attract efficient people towards teaching profession and to retain the committed teachers in the same profession their job satisfaction level has to be improved by offering decent salary, convenient working time, providing necessary freedom and assistance for their professional growth etc. The findings further implies a mere satisfaction of the job is always associated with contentment.

Teachers' Efficiency

Table 2 presents the level of teachers' work efficiency.

Table 2. Teachers' Efficiency

No.	Statement	WM	Description
1	How much can you do to get through to the most difficult students?	3.84	Quite A Bit
2	How much can you do to help your students think critically?	3.77	Quite A Bit
3	How much can you do to control disruptive behavior in the classroom?	3.83	Quite A Bit
4	How much can you do to motivate students who show low interest in school work?	3.88	Quite A Bit
5	To what extent can you make your expectations clear about student behavior?	3.75	Quite A Bit
6	How much can you do to get students believe they can do well in school work?	3.91	Quite A Bit
7	How well can you respond to difficult questions from your students?	3.77	Quite A Bit
8	How well can you establish routines to keep activities running smoothly?	3.82	Quite A Bit
9	How much can you do to help your students' value learning?	3.94	Quite A Bit
10	How much can you gauge your student comprehension of what you have taught?	3.83	Quite A Bit
11	To what extent can you craft good questions for your students	3.84	Quite A Bit
12	How much can you do to foster student creativity	3.80	Quite A Bit
13	How much can you do to get children to follow classroom rules?	3.82	Quite A Bit
14	How much can you do to improve the understanding of a student who is falling	3.81	Quite A Bit
15	How much can you do to calm a student who is disruptive or noisy?	3.81	Quite A Bit
16	How well can you establish a classroom management system with each group of students?	3.84	Quite A Bit
17	How much can you do to adjust your lessons to the proper level for individual students?	3.85	Quite A Bit
18	How much can you use from a variety of assessment strategies?	3.82	Quite A Bit
19	How well can you keep a few problem students from ruining the entire lesson?	3.76	Quite A Bit
20	To what extent can you provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused?	3.75	Quite A Bit
21	How well can you respond to defiant students?	3.66	Quite A Bit
22	How much can you assist families in helping their children do well in school?	3.64	Quite A Bit
23	How well can you implement alternative strategies in your classroom?	3.80	Quite A Bit
24	How well can you provide appropriate challenges for every capable student?	3.76	Quite A Bit
	AWM	3.81	Quite A Bit

The foregoing table disclosed the responses of the teachers as to their level of efficiency which revealed an over-all result of "Quite A Bit" with an average weighted mean of 3.81. In the indicator "how much can you do to get students believe they can do well in school work?" garnered a weighted mean of 3.94 which means teachers believed to get satisfied described as quite a bit to their present work as to facilitating learners learning activity in school. The lowest score of 3.64 among all indicators is "how much can you assist families in helping their children do well in school?" interpreted as quite a bit. The findings would mean that teachers could no longer assist the parents of the students due to the fact of the heavy workload assigned to them. In other words, there was an ancillary work assigned to the latter. The implication of this findings is that there must be a coordination between parents and the teachers. Likewise, teachers should spare time to conduct home visitation if not to reach out the parents in other means of communication.

This further implies that close coordination and communication is indispensable. This claim is supported with the study of Demirtaú (2010) which he revealed that it is expected that a school which has teachers with high level of job satisfaction and efficiency to work gives qualified education and brings up successful students.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it could be concluded that the secondary teachers in the Districts of Naval, Division of Biliran were just satisfied and quite a bit efficient of their work performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

School heads are encouraged to actively support, work and collaborate with teachers for the betterment and improvement of the teachers in terms of job satisfaction and efficiency of their work performance.

There should be a peer mentoring and/or counselling for the teachers. Proper and adequate technical assistance should also be provided to teachers, most especially those with low performance at school.

School heads should implement the designed Training and Development Program for teachers for the satisfaction and efficiency of teachers in their teaching job.

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